

Optimum Conditions for Fermentation of Isolated Bacteria and Its Application in Vinegar Fermentation of Grape Juice

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Abstract

Vinegar is a precious food additive and complement as well as effective preservative against food spoilage. Traditional vinegar production has been improved using various natural substrates and fruits such as grape, date and coconut. So the production of vinegar from grape juice by fermentation with optimum conditions has been studied. The study includes determination of optimum conditions for fermentation of isolated bacteria in industrial broth medium and vinegar fermentation of grape juice by optimum condition of isolated bacteria with three different fermentation processes contain natural anaerobic and aerobic fermentation, natural anaerobic and by adding bacteria culture aerobic fermentation and by adding yeast and bacteria culture for anaerobic and aerobic fermentation were studied. The optimum conditions of isolated bacteria were determined by varying the pH 3,4 and 5 and by varying the inoculum size 5%, 10% and 15%. The optimum culture age of isolated bacteria was also determined by observing at day 1,2,3 and 4 culture ages. The observed optimum conditions of isolated bacteria was pH 3, inoculum size 5% and 3,4 day culture age. From the various vinegar fermentation processes, acid % present in vinegar were 2.912, 2.594 and 5.9525 for fermentation procedure 1,2 and 3. The maximum acid %, 5.9525 present in vinegar was observed from procedure 3 after aerobic fermentation. Sugar content present in grape juice is 1.4731% by DNS method. After anaerobic fermentation, obtained wine contains sugar 1.037% for fermentation procedure 1,2 and 0.2712% for fermentation procedure 3. In addition, determination of antimicrobial activities of vinegar by agar well diffusion (agar disc) method, antioxidant activity by DPPH method and total phenolic content by Folin-Ciocalteu method were also studied. The antimicrobial activities of various vinegar were determined by agar well diffusion method with six test organism, *Bacillus Subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Candida albicans* and *Escherichia coli*. The highest inhibition zone was present for vinegar sample 3 obtained from fermentation process 3 compared to other two fermentation processes and three vinegar market samples. Antioxidant activity of various vinegar was determined by DPPH method. From IC_{50} values of vinegar obtained from three different fermentation processes and three vinegar market samples, the lowest IC_{50} value (0.4163 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was present for vinegar sample 2 obtained from fermentation process 2 and IC_{50} value of Natural lime vinegar (159.64 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was highest. Total phenolic content of vinegar was determined by Folin-Ciocalteu method. The highest phenolic content (0.0968 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was present for vinegar obtained from three different fermentation processes. The lowest total phenolic content (0.0102 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was present for natural lime vinegar market sample. The overlaid UV-visible spectra of various vinegar comparison with the anthocyanin standard cyanidin 3-O-rutinoside indicates that sample 1,2 and 3 show the absorption maximum at 520 nm given by the anthocyanin, whereas in the market samples no maxima at 520 nm can be observed.

Keywords: Grape, *acetobacter*, optimum condition, fermentation, vinegar

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Introduction

Vinegar is essentially a dilute solution of acetic acid made from fermentation process. Vinegar was made by using sugary substances by alcoholic and subsequent acetic fermentation. Vinegar can be produced by different methods and from various raw materials. Wine (white, red, and sherry wine), cider, fruit musts, pure alcohol are used as substrates (Morales *et al.*, 2001). *Acetobacter aceti* is mainly involved in vinegar production (Buchanan *et al.*, 1974). Sugar content was the primary indicator of grape ripeness (Eisenman, 1999). Acetic acid bacteria are well known for their ability to spoil wines because they can produce large amounts of acetic acid from ethanol and other compounds present in wines (Joyeux *et al.*, 1984; Drysdale *et al.*, 1989). Acetic acid bacteria are a large group of obligate aerobic gram negative bacteria with the ability to oxidize ethanol to acetic acid (Sharafi *et al.*, 2010). The optimum temperature for most bacteria is 20 °C to 30 °C (Beheshti-Maal and Shafiee, 2010). Acetic acid bacteria were present at all stages of wine making from the mature grape through vinification to conservation (Joyeux *et al.*, 1984). The strains of acetic acid bacteria are useful for vinegar production, however, lack of defined pure starter cultures is due to problem in strain isolation, cultivation and preservation of vinegar bacteria (Kadere *et al.*, 2008). Preserving vinegar depend on rate of acetic acid production, inherent capacity of *Acetobacter aceti* to convert alcohol to acetic acid, the amount of ethyl alcohol, the temperature and the amount of aeration of surface area of the growth material (Gullo *et al.*, 2008).

The present work deals with the study of optimum conditions of fermentation for the production of vinegar from grape juice by isolated *Acetobacter aceti* from the grapes.

Figure 1. Acetic acid forming bacteria

Figure 2. Grape sample

Aim

To study optimum conditions for fermentation of isolated acetic acid producing bacteria and its application in vinegar fermentation of grape juice.

Materials and Methods

Experimental comprises of three parts. The first part is concerned with sampling of grape. The second part contains determination of optimum conditions of isolated bacteria for fermentation and fermentation of grape juice by various processes. The third part is concerned with determination of antimicrobial activities, antioxidant activities and total phenolic content in various vinegar and comparison of the anthocyanin contents in different vinegar sample. They were conducted at Pharmaceutical and Food Research Department.

Sampling of Grape

Grape samples (Figure 2) were purchased from Thirimingalar Market, Yangon Region, originally from Yamethin Township, Mandalay Region and crushed to get juice by using blender.

Botanical Aspect of grape

Botanical Name : *Vitis vinifera* Linn.
 Family : Vitaceae
 Genus : *Vitis*
 Species : *V. vinifera*

Determination of optimum conditions of isolated bacteria for fermentation by various inoculum sizes and pH.

BHI broth medium was placed in conical flask, sterilized in sterilizer at 121 °C, cooled, added bacteria culture, placed in shaker and measured optical density with UV spectrophotometer wavelength 540 nm at every six hour for one day. Inoculum size 5 %, 10 % and 15 % of the obtained seed medium were transferred to industrial broth (pH 3, 4, 5) and fermented in shaker. Fermentation broth was titrated with standard sodium hydroxide and calculated acid percentage.

Determination of optimum condition of *Acetobacter* for fermentation by various culture age

BHI broth medium was placed in conical flask, divided four portions, sterilized in sterilizer (121 °C), cooled, added bacteria with various culture age to each portion and placed in shaker for one day. The obtained seed media (5%) were transferred to industrial broth (pH 3) and fermented in shaker (200 rpm). Fermentation broth was titrated with standard sodium hydroxide and calculated acid percentage.

Preparation of the various culture age of isolated bacteria

Four GYC agar slants were taken and isolated bacteria was added and then placed in incubator. Each slant was then transferred into refrigerator after keeping 1, 2, 3 and 4 days in incubator. In this way, *Acetobacter aceti* cultures of different ages were obtained.

Figure 3. Anaerobic fermentation

Figure 4. Aerobic fermentation

Vinegar fermentation of grape juice by various processes

Procedure (1)

Predetermined Sugar % in grape juice was subjected to anaerobic fermentation (25 °C) about 7 days. Sugar %, alcohol % and pH of wine were determined. Bacteria culture inoculum size (5 %) was added and then subjected to aerobic fermentation (30°C) with aeration rate 7.3 mL/s. Acid % and pH content in obtained vinegar were measured daily.

Procedure (2)

Predetermined Sugar % in grape juice was subjected to anaerobic fermentation (25 °C) about 7 days. Wine was obtained. Sugar %, alcohol % and pH of wine were determined, then subjected to aerobic fermentation (30 °C) with aeration rate 7.3 mL/s. Acid % and pH content in obtained vinegar were measured daily.

Procedure (3)

Predetermined Sugar % in grape juice was added *S.cerevisiae* (1.5 %) and then subjected to anaerobic fermentation (25 °C). Wine was obtained. Sugar %, alcohol % and pH of wine were determined. Bacteria culture inoculum size (5 %) was added and then subjected to aerobic fermentation (30 °C) with aeration rate 14.6 mL/s. Acid % and pH content in obtained vinegar were measured daily.

Determination of Antibacterial Activities of Natural Vinegar from Various Fermentation Processes by Agar Well Diffusion Method

Nutrient agar was prepared according to the method described by Cruickshank, 1975, Nutrient agar was boiled and 20-25 mL of the medium was poured into the test tube and plugged with cotton wool and sterilized at 121°C for 15 minutes in an autoclave. After this, the tubes were cooled down to 30-35 °C and poured into the sterilized petri dishes and 0.1-0.2 mL of the test organisms were added into the dishes. The agar was allowed to set for 2-3 hours; then 10 mm agar wells were made by the help of sterilized agar well cutter. After that, about 0.2 mL of the sample was introduced into the agar well and incubated at 37°C for the 24 hours. The inhibition zone which appeared around the agar well, indicated the presence of antimicrobial activity.

Screening of Antioxidant Activity of Various Natural Vinegars by using DPPH Free Radical Scavenging Assay

DPPH radical scavenging activity was determined by UV spectrophotometric method. Control solution was prepared by mixing the DPPH (1.5 mL) with ethanol (1.5 mL) using vortex mixer. This solution was used to measure the absorbance of control solution (A).

The sample solution was also prepared by mixing thoroughly 1.5 mL of 60 μM DPPH solution and 1.5 mL each of the test sample solutions using vortex mixer. In this way nine sample solutions were obtained for measurement of absorbance of sample solution (B).

Blank solution was prepared by mixing each of the test sample solution (1.5 mL) with 95 % ethanol (1.5 mL) using vortex mixer. These nine blank solutions were obtained for measurement of absorbance of blank solution (C).

The solutions were allowed to stand at room temperature for 30 minutes. After 30 minutes, the absorbance of these solutions was measured at 517 nm by using UV spectrophotometer. Absorbance measurements were done in triplicate for each solution and

then mean values so obtained were used to calculate percent inhibition of oxidation by the following equation.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{A - (B - C)}{A} \times 100$$

Where,

% Inhibition = % inhibition of test sample

A = absorbance of control solution

B = absorbance of sample solution

C = absorbance of blank solution

Then, IC₅₀ (50% inhibitory concentration) values were also calculated by linear regressive excel program.

Determination of Total Phenolic Content as Gallic Acid of Various Natural Vinegar by Spectrophotometric Method using Folin Ciocalteu Reagent

For determination of phenolic content, 1 mL of vinegar was mixed well with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent 0.5 mL and 20 % Na₂CO₃ 1.5 mL. The mixtures were made up volume to 10 mL by distilled water and allow standing at room temperature in the dark for 2 hours. The absorbance was detected at 760 nm. To prepare a calibration curve, 0.1 mg/ mL gallic acid was used as a standard (Table 1) (Cicco, 2009).

Table 1. Volumes (mL) of Reagents Mixed for Preparation of Five Standard Solution for Construction of Total Phenolic Calibration Curve

Reagent	Standard Solution				
	1	2	3	4	5
Gallic acid 0.1 mg/ mL	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
Distilled water	7.8	7.6	7.4	7.2	7.0
Folin-Ciocalteu	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
20 % Na ₂ CO ₃	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5

Left in the dark for 2 hours, A₇₆₀

Results and Discussion

Optimum conditions of *Acetobacter* for fermentation by various inoculum sizes and pH

Bacteria growth and acid production conditions were optimized based on optimal inoculum size, pH and culture age of bacteria. The optical density of seed medium was shown in Figure 5 and Table 2. At every six hours optical density increased showing increase in bacteria culture. The optimum conditions of *Acetobacter* for fermentation by various inoculum sizes and pH were shown in Figures (6, 7, 8) and Tables (3, 4, 5). From these tables, the highest acid % was observed for 5% inoculum size for various pH. The highest acid % was observed for pH 3 compared to pH 4 and 5. The observed optimum condition of *Acetobacter* was pH 3 and inoculum size 5%.

Optimum condition of *Acetobacter* for fermentation by various culture age

The optimum condition of *Acetobacter* for fermentation by various culture age was shown in Figure 9 and Table 6. From this table the highest acid % was present for 3 and 4 days culture age. The optimum condition was observed in three and four days culture age.

Fermentation of grape juice by various processes

Contents of alcohol, sugar % and pH were measured in wine obtained from the primary fermentation. The resultant data was reported in Table 8.

The acid percentage daily present from vinegar fermentation by various processes was shown in Figure 10 and Table 7. From this table the highest acid percentage in vinegar was observed for procedure 3 and the lowest acid % in vinegar present for procedure 2. Aerobic fermentation rate of production of acid depends on temperature, aeration rate and surface area of the fermented medium.

Table 2. Optical Density for Seed Medium

Time (hours)	Optical density
0	0.296
6	1.329
12	1.381
18	1.416
24	1.458

Optical density was measured by UV spectrophotometer at 600 nm

Optical density for seed medium

Table 3. Variation of Acid Percent with Time of Fermentation for Different Inoculum Sizes at pH 3

Inoculum size	Acid % at different fermentation time (day)			
	1	2	3	4
15 %	2.6284	2.7599	2.7599	2.8256
10 %	2.5627	2.6284	2.6941	2.8256
5 %	2.6941	2.6941	2.8256	2.8913

Figure 6.

Variation of acid percent with time of fermentation for different inoculum sizes at pH 3

Table 4. Variation of Acid Percent with Time of Fermentation for Different Inoculum Sizes at pH 4

Inoculum size	Acid % at different fermentation time (day)			
	1	2	3	4
15 %	2.1027	2.1684	2.2342	2.2999
10 %	2.1684	2.1684	2.2342	2.2999
5 %	2.2342	2.2999	2.3656	2.3656

Figure 7. Variation of acid percent with time of fermentation for different inoculum sizes at pH 4

Table 5. Variation of Acid Percent with Time of Fermentation for Different Inoculum Sizes at pH 5

Inoculum size	Acid % at different fermentation time (day)			
	1	2	3	4
15 %	0.8542	0.8542	0.9856	0.9856
10 %	0.9199	0.9199	0.98566	0.9856
5 %	0.8542	0.9199	1.0513	1.0513

Figure 8. Variation of acid percent with time of fermentation for different inoculums size at pH 5

Table 6. Variation of Acid Percent with Time of Fermentation for Different Inoculum Ages at pH 3

Culture age	Acid % at different fermentation time (day)			
	1	2	3	4
1	2.34	2.34	2.34	2.70
2	2.52	2.64	2.64	2.76
3	2.58	2.64	2.64	2.76
4	2.58	2.64	2.64	2.76

Table 7. Daily Content of Acid % (w/v) in Vinegar for Different Fermentation Processes

Procedure	Acid % at different fermentation time (day)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Procedure(1)	0.6882	0.6882	0.6882	0.7411	1.7999	2.9117
Procedure(2)	0.6352	0.6352	0.6352	0.6352	1.3764	2.5941
Procedure(3)	0.5336	0.6157	0.8621	5.5007	5.6649	5.9525

FFigure 9. Variation of acid percent with time of fermentation for different inoculum ages at pH 3

Table 8. Contents of Sugar and Alcohol and pH Values in Wine Samples by Different Fermentation Processes

Fermentation Processes	Sugar content (%)	Alcohol content (%)	pH
1	1.037	7	3.88
2	1.037	7	3.95
3	0.2712	5	3.99

Sugar content in grape juice is 1.4731 %

Figure 10. Bar graph showing daily content of acid % in vinegar for different fermentation processes

Antimicrobial Activities of Three Different Natural Vinegars from Various Fermentation Processes and Three Natural Vinegar Market Samples

Basal test organisms used in this research were supported from the Pharmaceutical and Food Research Department for the determination of the antimicrobial activity. These include *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Pseudomonas aureginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Candida albicans* and *Escherichia-coli*. The results of antimicrobial activities of vinegar samples are reported in Table 9, and Figures 11, 12. The result of antimicrobial activities of three different market samples are reported in Table 10 and Figures 13, 14, 15.

From the results of Table 9, the decreasing order of antimicrobial activities of different samples in sample 3 > sample 1 > sample 2. This coincides with the decreasing order of acetic

acid contents Table 7 and Figures 10 of these samples. Consequently, it deduced that the higher the acetic acid content, the higher the antimicrobial activity of a vinegar sample.

It was observed that the vinegar sample (3) from the present works, as well as the market samples exhibited potent antimicrobial activities (Figures 13, 14, 15 and Table 10) against all the microorganisms tested, namely, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Candida albicans* and *E. coli*.

All the vinegar samples tested contained similarly acetic acid (about 5 %). This may be the reason why they exhibited similar antimicrobial activities.

Figure 11. Photograph showing antimicrobial activity of natural vinegar from three different fermentation processes with six test organisms

Table 9. Antimicrobial Activities of Natural Vinegars from Three Different Fermentation Processes

Samples	Inhibition Zone Diameters (mm)					
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Sample (1)	30 (+++)	40 (+++)	25 (+++)	27 (+++)	28 (+++)	29 (+++)
Sample (2)	15 (++)	25 (+++)	18 (++)	16 (++)	16 (++)	14 (+)
Sample (3)	45 (+++)	55 (+++)	45 (+++)	42 (+++)	35 (+++)	37 (+++)
Control	-	-	-	-	-	-

Agar well – 10 mm	Organism
10 mm ~ 14 mm (+)	(1) <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (N.C.T.C-8236)
15 mm ~ 19 mm (++)	(2) <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (N.C.P.C-6371)
20 mm above (+++)	(3) <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (6749)
	(4) <i>Bacillus pumilus</i> (N.C.I.B-8982)
	(5) <i>Candida albican</i>
	(6) <i>E. coli</i> (N.C.I.B-8134)

Figure 12. Bar graph showing inhibition zone diameter of natural vinegar from three different fermentation processes against six test organisms

Figure 14. Photograph showing antimicrobial activity of three market samples natural vinegar against *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 13. Antimicrobial activity vinegar sample (3) and three types of natural vinegar from market with six test organisms

Table 10. Antimicrobial Activities of Natural Vinegar Sample (3) Compared to Three Types of Natural Vinegar

Samples	Inhibition Zone Diameters (mm)					
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Natural Lime Vinegar	41 (+++)	35 (+++)	36 (+++)	48 (+++)	40 (+++)	36 (+++)
SW Apple Cider Vinegar	48 (+++)	31 (+++)	40 (+++)	48 (+++)	38 (+++)	36 (+++)
Woh Hup Red Vinegar	47 (+++)	30 (+++)	44 (+++)	50 (+++)	42 (+++)	36 (+++)
Sample (3)	50 (+++)	55 (+++)	45 (+++)	50 (+++)	40 (+++)	36 (+++)

Agar well – 10 mm

10 mm ~ 14 mm (+)

15 mm ~ 19 mm (++)

20 mm above (+++)

Organism

(1) *Bacillus subtilis* (N.C.T.C-8236)(2) *Staphylococcus aureus* (N.C.P.C-6371)(3) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (6749)(4) *Bacillus pumilus* (N.C.I.B-8982)(5) *Candida albican*(6) *E. coli* (N.C.I.B-8134)

Figure 15. Bar graph showing antimicrobial activities of natural vinegar sample (3) compared to three market samples of natural vinegar

Antioxidant Activity of Natural Vinegars from Three Different Fermentation Processes and Three Natural Vinegar Market Samples

Table 11. Oxidative Inhibition % for Different Concentrations and IC₅₀ Values of Different Vinegar Samples

Sample	Oxidative Inhibition % at different concentration (□g/mL)										IC ₅₀ (□g/mL)
	039	0.78	1.56	3.125	6.25	12.5	25	50	100	200	
Sample (1)	33.19	51.33	65.49	84.51	96.02	95.58	92.92	188.94	-	-	0.7514
Sample (2)	48.59	69.49	72.01	83.36	96.65	97.27	97.62	97.54	-	-	0.4163
Sample (3)	-	35.82	49.28	82.21	91.11	90.87	159.86	-	-	-	1.606
Apple cider	-	-15.15	2.69	7.74	20.20	31.31	64.98	92.93	92.59	95.29	17.53
Red	-	-27.62	-24.13	-23.08	-2.10	7.34	30.07	51.05	86.01	58.04	48.38
Lime	-	3.67	5.51	4.46	7.35	8.92	10.50	26.25	34.65	60.10	159.64

Table 12. IC₅₀ Values of Various Vinegar Samples

Sample	IC ₅₀ (□g/ mL)
Sample (1)	0.7514
Sample (2)	0.4163
Sample (3)	1.606
SW Apple cider vinegar	17.53
Woh Hup Red vinegar	48.38
Natural Lime vinegar	159.64
Vitamin C	0.673

Figure 16. Bar graph showing IC₅₀ values of various vinegar samples

Total Phenolic Content in Vinegars from Three Different Fermentation Processes and Three Natural Vinegar Market Samples

Total phenolic content in the vinegar samples was determined by Folin-Ciocalteu method. The absorbance was measured by UV-visible spectrophotometer at the wavelength 760 nm. The blue coloured complex was formed by reduction of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, (phosphomolybdic-phosphotungstic) acid by the phenolic group. The absorbance values for different gallic acid working standard solutions were presented in Table 13 and Figure 17.

Total phenolic contents in the vinegar samples were reported in Table 14 and Figure 18.

The decreasing order of total phenolic contents in thus, sample 1 = sample 2 = sample 3 > Woh Hup Red Vinegar > SW Apple Cider Vinegar > Natural Lime Vinegar.

Table 13. Absorbance of Different Gallic Acid Working Standard Solutions

No.	Concentration (mg/mL)	Absorbance
1.	0.02	0.87512
2.	0.04	1.80969
3.	0.06	2.63513
4.	0.08	3.43616
5.	0.10	3.99988

Figure 17. Calibration curve of gallic acid standard for determination of total phenolic content

Table 14. Total Phenolic Contents in Various Vinegar Samples

Sample	Content ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)
Sample (1)	0.0968
Sample (2)	0.0968
Sample (3)	0.0968
SW Apple cider vinegar	0.0332
Woh Hup Red vinegar	0.0349
Natural Lime vinegar	0.0102

Figure 18. Bar graph showing total phenolic contents in various vinegar

Comparison of the Anthocyanin Contents in Different Vinegar Samples

Figure 19. Overlaid UV-visible spectra of different vinegar samples

Figure 20. Overlaid UV-visible spectra of different vinegar samples together with the spectrum of standard cyanidin 3-O-rutinoside

The overlaid UV-visible spectra comparison with the anthocyanin standard cyanidin 3-O-rutinoside (Longo *et al.*, 2006) (Chuanguang, 2010) indicates that samples 1, 2 and 3 show the absorption maximum at 520 nm given by the anthocyanin, whereas in the market samples no maxima at 520 nm can be observed (Figure 19 and 20).

Conclusion

The present study showed that observed optimum condition of isolated bacteria was pH 3, inoculum size 5 % and 3 days culture age for fermentation in industrial broth medium. Acid % present in vinegar were 2.912, 2.594 and 5.9525 respectively, for fermentation procedures 1, 2 and 3. From the study of the vinegar fermentation of grape juice by various processes, the maximum acid %, 5.9525 was observed in vinegar from procedure 3 after aerobic fermentation. Sugar content present in grape juice was 1.4731 %. After anaerobic fermentation, obtained wine contained 1.037 % of sugar for procedure 1, 2 and 0.2712 % of sugar for yeast added anaerobic, fermentation and bacteria culture added aerobic fermentation. From the IC_{50} values of vinegar obtained from various fermentation processes and three vinegar market samples obtained from City Mart, the lowest IC_{50} value (0.4163 μ g/mL) was present from vinegar sample 2 obtained from fermentation procedure 2 and the IC_{50} value of natural lime vinegar (159.64 μ g/mL) was highest. The highest inhibition zone of antibacterial activities was present for vinegar sample 3 obtained from fermentation procedure 3, compared to other two fermentation procedure and three market vinegar samples obtained from City Mart. The highest total phenolic content (0.0968 μ g/mL) was present for vinegar obtained from various fermentation processes. The lowest total phenolic content (0.0102 μ g/mL) was present for natural lime vinegar market sample. The overlaid UV-visible spectra of various vinegar samples compared with the anthocyanin standard cyanidin 3-O-rutinoside indicate that samples 1, 2 and 3 show the absorption maximum at 520 nm given by the anthocyanin, whereas in the market samples no maxima at 520 nm can be observed. From the above mentioned, vinegar

obtained from three different fermentation processes in the present work is better quality than three natural vinegar market samples due to their better total phenolic content than three vinegar market samples.

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